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Genes of the p53 family repressed during tumor suppression.

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The master tumor suppressor p53 is described as guardian of the genome resulting from its ability to protect the cell from genotoxic insults and changes in the cell cycle that de-restrict licensed cell division. Activation of p53 has transcriptional consequences with functions in the cell cycle, like activation of the *CDKN* cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor genes, as well as repressive transcriptional consequences, like silencing expression of genes that encode enzymes that catalyze nucleotide synthesis to replicate the daughter strand (DNA) to halt cell cycle progression. Separate from but related to its cellular transcriptional targets, p53 exists within a broader family of genes that belong to the p53 family that are less well-described. We measured total transcription in human cells genetically depleted of p53 to identify p53 family genes members and understand the relative changes in their quantities. We describe here genes of the p53 family silenced during tumor suppression.

Results

We identified genes of the p53 family, repressed by p53 during tumor suppression, by genetic depletion of p53 in human cells *in vitro*.

Figure 1: Depletion of p53 in human breast epithelial cells (MCF10A) results in activation of the tumor protein p53 inducible protein 3, *TP53I3*.

GSE162341

n=2 MCF10A, with wild-type p53

n=1 MCF10A, with p53 shRNA

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7157	0.0113304	0.736	2.53234	1.863011	908.67	TP53	172/14517	98.8
9540	0.6818039	1.635	-0.410003	-0.670481	102.29	TP53I3	1786/14517	87.7
51002	0.2426353	1.318	-1.168425	-1.539914	145.68	TPRKB	2024/14517	86.1
11257	0.3999864	2.491	-0.841645	-2.096351	30.19	TP53TG1	5897/14517	59.4
100144748	0.3055156	5.787	-1.024677	-5.929736	3.71	KLLN	7680/14517	47.1
51499	0.6670828	1.681	-0.430155	-0.72289	108.84	TRIAP1	9347/14517	35.6
7158	0.8919937	0.765	-0.135782	-0.103816	592.75	TP53BP1	10306/14517	29.0
90313	0.1840046	5.398	-1.328525	-7.170737	8.78	TP53I13	11581/14517	20.2
81572	0.8695024	1.953	-0.164291	-0.320821	51.75	PDRG1	13273/14517	8.6

Figure 2: Depletion of p53 in human breast cancer cells (MCF7) results in activation of tumor protein p53 inducible nuclear protein 1, *TP53INP1*.

GSE72359

n=3 control (MCF7; DMSO vehicle; control vector)

n=3 MCF7 (MCF7; DMSO vehicle; p53 shRNA)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201746_at	1.01e-04	10.0642112	1.575312	3.26195527	TP53	37/54675	99.9
225912_at	1.13e-02	-3.7520774	-2.402471	-0.97122614	TP53INP1	1299/ 54675	97.6
223919_at	3.70e-02	-2.7454847	-3.571168	-1.1840442	TP53AIP1	3259/54675	94.0

Discussion

We identified here the salient p53 gene family members controlled by p53 in tumor suppression using a genetic loss-of-function approach in human cells.